

Dimensional Change of Metal Matrix Composites Subjected to Creep/Thermal Cycle Loading

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ABSTRACT

Dimensional change in short fiber metal matrix composites(MMCs) under creep/thermal cycle loading is studied analytically and experimentally. The model simulates an elastic-creeping matrix and elastic fibers and predicts strain per thermal cycle by considering the combined effects of the temperature-induced internal stress, applied stress and the diffusional relaxation of the internal stress generated by the plastic strain in the matrix. The volume-averaged internal stress in the matrix is calculated by using dislocation punching model. The thermal cycling creep test is performed by thermal cycler with a constant stress cam. The predictions based on the present model are in good agreements with the experimental results.

1. INTRODUCTION

A metal matrix composite consists of a matrix metal and reinforcements and its mechanical properties are normally superior to those of the unreinforced metal except for the fracture toughness and the thermal cycling resistance. The main reason for this defect of MMC is the mismatch of the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) between the matrix metal and reinforcements[1]. It is well known that the combination of relatively small applied stresses and cyclic thermal loading can result in increased creep rates and superplastic deformations in metal matrix composites[2]. Even without an applied stress, a detrimental dimensional change has been observed in a number of thermal cycled metal matrix composite systems. These effects are important aspects for study in the assessment of MMCs as candidates for high temperature structural applications requiring dimensional stability and attributed to internal stresses that are repeatedly developed during thermal cycling due to the CTE mismatch. Although a series of experiments on the thermal cycling creep behavior of discontinuous MMCs have been made, the analytical model to predict dimensional change still remains to be made.

For the analysis of the enhanced creep rate under creep/thermal cycle loading, the determination of internal stress is prerequisite. The existence of internal stress has been proved by the use of neutron diffraction method and the measurements of differences between compressive and tensile mechanical properties. High internal stresses generated at the interface between the fiber and matrix are readily relaxed to a lower stress state by the dislocation punching. This phenomenon has been observed in a SiC whisker/Al composite in situ transmission electron microscopy study[3,4]. Therefore, the internal stress needs to be estimated based on the stress field of the relaxed state.

The purpose of this work is to develop an analytical model to predict dimensional change of a short fiber MMC subjected to creep/thermal cycle loading and to compare with experimental results. In this model, we focus on the combined effects of the internal stress, externally applied stress and the relaxation of the stress induced by creep strain. The temperature-induced internal stress is calculated based on reference temperature by extending the Taya et al.'s dislocation

punching model [5, 6] and the matrix stress carried by externally applied stress is also calculated, where the Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method [7] and Mori-Tanaka's mean field theory [8] are used. Finally, the predictions will be compared with the experimental results.

2. ANALYTICAL MODEL

Since it is considered that fibers are purely elastic and the matrix is an elastic-creeping, the determination of the stresses carried by the matrix is a basis for the prediction of the dimensional change of a MMC under creep/thermal cycle loading. Those stresses are classified as the stress induced by temperature change, an applied stress and the stress generated by the creep strain in the matrix. The first is relaxed by dislocation punching, based on which it is calculated at each temperature on temperature profile of thermal cycling by using temperature-dependent yield stress. The amount of the second carried by the matrix is a function of material properties and fiber shape and calculated by using Eshelby type model. The last, called back stress, is assumed to be relaxed instantaneously by a relaxation mechanism such as interfacial diffusion and calculated by Eshelby type model as well. Finally, the strain per cycle is numerically calculated by using the equation of matrix creep, the power law of Dorn type.

2.1 MATRIX STRESS DUE TO TEMPERATURE CHANGE

When MMCs are fabricated at high temperature or annealed at a certain high temperature and cooled down to a lower temperature such as room temperature, residual stresses are generated in a MMC by the mismatch of the CTE between the matrix and fiber. These high internal stresses are partially relaxed by punching prismatic dislocation loops. In analyzing thermal cycling creep resistance of a short fiber MMC, the internal stress induced by temperature change is an important parameter and its magnitude during thermal cycling has been considered to be the yield strength of the matrix [9]. If the CTE mismatch strain generated by temperature change is small so that the yielding of the matrix metal is localized around fibers, then the assumption of general yielding of the matrix in the entire matrix domain is not valid. Thus, it is necessary to calculate the thermal residual stress for the case of the localized yielding during thermal cycling creep of a MMC. Although many models have been proposed to estimate the residual stress, they were confined to one-dimensional analysis, continuous fiber system or spherical particle system [10]. In this work, the thermal residual stress in the matrix is calculated by extending Taya et al. model for the finite volume fraction of fiber and using the concept of volume average of internal stress.

It is necessary to consider the relaxation mechanism of the temperature-induced stress so as to calculate the residual stress in the matrix due to temperature change. Upon cooling from reference temperature (T_A), the CTE mismatch strain is simulated by arrays of prismatic dislocation loops generated at the surface of fiber (Ω_1) as shown in Fig. 1 (a). These loops are punched out along the major axis (x_3) to relax localized high stress at fiber-matrix interface and located in equilibrium position. The punched-out loops are represented by another spheroid (Ω_2) inscribing the fiber (Ω_1) as shown in Fig. 1 (b). As shown in Fig. 2, these loops are replaced by eigenstrains $e^{1*} (= \{\alpha^*, \alpha^*, 0, 0, 0, 0\})$ and $e^{2*} (= \{0, 0, \alpha^*c/c', 0, 0, 0\})$ in Ω_1 and Ω_2 respectively, where α^* is the CTE mismatch strain based on ΔT shown in Fig. 3. The punching distance c' is determined by the balance of the punching and retarding forces:

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial c'} = - \frac{\partial W}{\partial c'} \quad (1)$$

where U and W denote the total potential energy and the total work done by the motion of the dislocation loops over the punching distance respectively and are expressed by

$$U = -\frac{1}{2} f C \cdot \left\{ (S^2 - I) \cdot e^{1**} \cdot e^{2*} + (S^1 - I) \cdot e^{1**} \cdot e^{2*} + (S^2 - I) \cdot e^{2*} \cdot (c' e^{2*} + e^{1*}) \right\} \quad (2)$$

$$W = \beta f k \left(\frac{c'}{c} - 1 \right) \alpha^* \quad (3)$$

where C , S , I , f , β , c and k denote the elastic moduli of matrix, Eshelby tensor, identity matrix, fiber volume fraction, aspect ratio of fiber, the major axis of fiber and flow stress of matrix and superscript 1 and 2 on S denote fiber and punched-out domain respectively. Since the punching distance is strongly dependent on the flow stress, temperature dependent flow stress is used. Once the punching distance is determined, the stresses σ^1 and σ^2 in Ω_2 - Ω_1 and D - Ω_2 are calculated as

$$\sigma^1 = C \cdot (S^1 - I) \cdot e^{1**} \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma^2 = C \cdot [(1-f_2)(S^2 - I) \cdot e^{2*} - f(S^1 - I) \cdot e^{1**}] \quad (5)$$

where f_2 and D denote the volume fraction of punched-out domain and composite domain respectively. Eqns. (4) and (5) gives the volume average of temperature-induced stress σ_m^T , i.e.,

$$\sigma_m^T = [(1-f_2)\sigma^2 + (f_2-f)\sigma^1] / (1-f) \quad (6)$$

The calculation result of Eqn. (6) at each temperature on temperature profile is curve-fitted as a function of temperature.

2.2 MATRIX STRESS DUE TO APPLIED STRESS

The stress externally applied to the composite material σ^o shown in Fig. 4 is shared by the matrix and fiber. The stresses carried by each component are determined by the mechanical properties of each component and fiber shape. By using Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method, the stresses distributed to matrix, σ_m^A , are easily calculated as

$$\sigma_m^A = \left\langle I + f C_m \cdot (S - I) \cdot \left\{ (C_f - C_m) \cdot [(1-f)S + fI] + C_m \right\}^{-1} \cdot (C_f - C_m) \cdot C_m^{-1} \right\rangle \cdot \sigma^o \quad (7)$$

where subscripts m and f denote matrix and fiber respectively.

2.3 MATRIX STRESS DUE TO CREEP STRAIN IN THE MATRIX

As creep strain is accumulated in the matrix domain, the matrix is hardened by the back stress due to geometrically necessary dislocations around fibers resulting from the homogeneous plastic deformation of the matrix and becomes more resistant to further plastic deformation. However, it has been also recognized that the back stress state is not stable and can be relaxed by some mechanisms. It is assumed that interfacial diffusion takes place and relaxes the buildup of back stress simultaneously[11]. Since the stress field in the fiber due to back stress and its diffusional relaxation becomes hydrostatic, it does not affect further plastic deformation of matrix[12].

The small amount of uniform creep strain in the matrix, de^c , and its diffusional strain in the fiber, de^d , induce the stresses in the fiber, $d\sigma^c = -(1-f)U \cdot de^c/f$ and $d\sigma^d = (1-f)U \cdot de^d/f$, respectively, where $U = f C_m \cdot (S - I) \cdot \left\{ (C_f - C_m) \cdot [(1-f)S + fI] + C_m \right\}^{-1} \cdot C_f \cdot B$ and $B = \{-.5, -.5, 1, 0, 0, 0\}$. From the requirement of the diffusional relaxation, the 1- and 3- components of stresses satisfy the following:

$$d\sigma_3^c + d\sigma_3^d = d\sigma_1^c + d\sigma_1^d \quad (8)$$

Eqn. (8) implies that the diffusional strain in the fiber is equal in magnitude to the creep strain in the matrix, i.e.,

$$de^c = de^d \tag{9}$$

Thus, the resultant matrix stress $d\sigma_m$, generated by the incremental creep and diffusional strains, is canceled out, i.e.,

$$d\sigma_m = U \cdot (de^c - de^d) = 0 \tag{10}$$

Figure 1. Arrays of prismatic dislocation loops (a) before punching (b) after punching

Figure 2. Stresses and eigenstrains after dislocation punching

Figure 3. Temperature change for temperature-induced stress calculation

Figure 4. Analytical model for a short fiber MMC with an applied stress σ^0

2.4 STRAIN PER THERMAL CYCLE

Since the creep resistance of silicon carbide is much higher than that of aluminum due to its high modulus and low diffusion rate, it is considered that SiC fibers do not deform plastically while Al matrix does during thermal cycling/creep. The creep rate of composite depends only on the matrix creep rate which obeys the power law of Dorn type. Eqns. (6), (7) and (10) give the matrix creep rate, i.e.,

$$\dot{\epsilon}_m = \frac{A}{T} [\sigma_m^T + \sigma_m^A]^n \exp\left(-\frac{Q}{RT}\right) \quad (11)$$

where A, T, R and Q are Dorn constant, temperature, gas constant and activation energy respectively and matrix stresses and strain are expressed in terms of equivalent quantities. Once the matrix creep rate is given, the composite strain per cycle ϵ_c is calculated by summing the creep and diffusional strains and numerically integrating Eqn. (11) over one thermal cycle, i.e.,

$$\epsilon_c = \int_0^{\tau} \dot{\epsilon}_m dt \quad (12)$$

where τ is duration of one thermal cycle.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Thermal cycling creep tests are performed on SiCp/A356-T71 Aluminum (SiC/Al) composite for two thermal cycles of $T_{max}=300^\circ\text{C}$ and 350°C using thermal cycler with a constant stress cam which compensates the instantaneous change of the cross-sectional area of specimen to maintain a constant stress during test [13]. A typical temperature profile shown in Fig. 5 is measured by the K-type thermocouple inserted into the specimen and is curve-fitted as a function of time and the material properties and parameters used for calculations are as follows: $f=0.2$, $E_{Al}=70$ GPa, $\nu_{Al}=0.33$, $\alpha_{Al}=23.6 \times 10^{-6}$, $E_{SiC}=427$ GPa, $\nu_{SiC}=0.17$, $\alpha_{SiC}=4.3 \times 10^{-6}$, $A=1522$, $n=4.7322$, $T_A=530$ °C, $Q=142$ KJ/mole [10,14]. Fig. 6 shows the predicted internal stress in the matrix

developed at each temperature during test and yield stress of the aluminum matrix versus temperature and implies the strong dependence of residual stress on the matrix yield stress.

Fig. 7 shows the analytical and experimental results in terms of strain per thermal cycle versus applied stress. In the higher thermal cycle of $T_{max}=350^{\circ}C$, it is considered to simplify the analysis and confirmed by SEM photomicrographs that short fibers are mostly oriented in direction of extrusion and their average aspect ratio is 2.2. Takao et al. have examined the effect of variable fiber aspect ratio on the stiffness and thermal expansion coefficients of a short fiber composite and concluded that the results predicted by using the average value of aspect ratio are not much different those of using actual variable aspect ratio unless the distribution of aspect ratio is extraordinarily scattered[15]. Thus, the use of the average aspect ratio in the present model is justified. For the higher thermal cycle of $T_{max}=350^{\circ}C$, the predicted results agree well with the experimental results except for the applied stress 32MPa. For the lower thermal cycle of $T_{max}=300^{\circ}C$, the predicted results agree reasonably well with the trend of the experimental results although they exceed the experimental results. This discrepancy can be explained as follows. First, it is assumed that the interfacial diffusion takes place instantaneously at each time during thermal cycling. According to Mori et al's model, its characteristic time is strongly dependent on the temperature and the calculation of characteristic times for several temperatures gives 0.5, 1.5, 5 and 20 seconds at $T=350, 300, 250$ and $200^{\circ}C$ respectively[12,16]. Thus, the recovery of back stress by diffusional relaxation is limited at low temperature so that the unrelaxed back stress in the matrix lowers the extent of the plastic deformation of the matrix. Secondly, it has been also known that although SiC fibers are randomly distributed in the matrix before test, they are reoriented in the direction of applied stress during test of $T_{max}=450^{\circ}C$ [2]. Nevertheless, it needs to be examined how the temperature affects the redistribution of fibers in the matrix. If its redistribution is not fully made in the direction of applied stress, the present model overestimates the temperature-induced matrix stress and underestimates the matrix stress due to applied stress. Since the former is larger than the latter below $300^{\circ}C$, predictions for the lower thermal cycle of $T_{max}=300^{\circ}C$ become higher than the experimental values.

Figure 5. Temperature profile measured during thermal cycling test

Figure 6. Yield and residual stresses of matrix metal vs. temperature

Figure 7. Comparison between the analytical and experimental results

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